

Electrochemical Oxidation of 5-Amino-3-methylisothiazole

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The electrochemical oxidation of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole has been studied in the phosphate buffers of pH 3.0–10.9 at pyrolytic graphite electrode. The product of electro-oxidation has been identified and a plausible mechanism suggested.

THE incorporation of isothiazole moiety in an organic compound has been found to increase its biological activity. Pencillines and cephalosporins synthesised with isothiazole ring system have found to possess activity comparable to ampicilline against gram-positive and gram-negative organisms¹. Isothiazole ring having substituents at position-3 and -5 has also been introduced in well-known drugs including phenothiazines, sulphonamides etc. having enhanced activity². An excellent review dealing with preparation and uses of isothiazoles has also appeared in the literature³. Literature survey revealed that the electrochemical behaviour of isothiazoles has not attracted much attention. In this paper, electrochemical behaviour of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole (1), which is claimed to be herbicide⁴, is presented at pyrolytic graphite electrode. The product of electrode reaction has been identified using ir and mass spectra, and a plausible mechanism for the electrode reaction is suggested.

Experimental

5-Amino-3-methylisothiazole hydrochloride (Aldrich) was used as such. Equipments used for linear and cyclic sweep voltammetry and controlled potential electrolysis were essentially the same as described elsewhere⁵. Spectral studies were carried out using a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer. The pyrolytic graphite electrode was prepared by the method reported earlier⁶ having an area of ~ 2.0 mm². The value of n (number of electrons involved in oxidation) were determined by the electrolysis of 0.1–0.2 mg of compound 1 in a three-compartment cell using cylindrical platinum gauze as counter electrode, pyrolytic graphite plate (6×1 cm²) as working electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The change in current with time was monitored and the value of n was calculated by the

method of Lingane⁷. All the experiments were carried out in phosphate buffers⁸ of ionic strength 0.5 *M*.

The stock solution (5 mM) of compound 1 was prepared in methanol (AnalaR). For recording the curves, the stock solution (1.0 ml) was mixed with buffer solution (9.0 ml) of appropriate pH. Nitrogen was bubbled for 8–10 min before recording the curves.

The identification of product was achieved by electrolyzing compound 1 (5–6 mg) in a buffer of desired pH at potentials more positive to oxidation peak. The progress of electrolysis was monitored by recording cyclic voltammograms at different interval of times. When the oxidation peak completely disappeared, electrolysis was stopped and the electrolysed solution was transferred from the cell and lyophilised. The dried material was extracted with ether (3×10 ml) and the concentrated ether extract was analysed by ir and mass spectra.

Results and Discussion

Linear sweep voltammetry of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole at a sweep rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ exhibited one well-defined oxidation peak in the pH range 3.0–10.9. The peak potential of this peak was dependent on pH and shifted towards less positive potential with increase in pH indicating thereby the involvement of protons in the electrode reaction. The E_p vs pH plot was linear (Fig. 1) and exhibited a break around pH 5.6. The peak potential can be represented by the relations,

$$E_p \text{ (pH 3.0–5.6)} = [1.17 - 0.067 \text{ pH}] \text{ V vs SCE}$$

$$E_p \text{ (pH 5.6–10.9)} = [0.96 - 0.034 \text{ pH}] \text{ V vs SCE}$$

In cyclic sweep voltammetry at a scan rate of 200 mV s⁻¹, compound 1 exhibited one well-defined oxidation peak (11a). In the reverse sweep, one cathodic peak (1c) appeared at around zero volt which formed a quasi reversible couple with peak 1a observed on the subsequent sweep towards positive potential. Some of the typical voltammograms are presented in Fig. 2. The peak potentials

Fig. 1 Variation of peak potential with pH for the voltammetric peaks of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole: (Δ) 1c, (O) 1a and (\bullet) 11a.

of peak 1a and 1c were also dependent on pH and exhibited a linear E_p vs pH relationship as shown in Fig. 1. It was interesting to observe that in the acidic pH range when the direction of sweep was changed after recording peak 11a, an ill-defined peak (11c) forming an irreversible couple was also observed. Peak 11c was clearly visible at sweep rate $> 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ and its height increased with the increase in sweep rate and the ratio of i_{pc}/i_{pa} reached to maximum value of 0.4 at a sweep rate of 500 mV s^{-1} . To confirm whether peak 1c is due to the reduction of the product formed in peak 11a process or due to an independent reduction of compound 1, cyclic voltammograms were also recorded by initiating the sweep in negative direction. The absence of peak 1c clearly indicates that compound 1 does not undergo reduction in the available potential range of pyrolytic graphite and hence peak 1c is due to reduction of the product formed in peak 11a reaction.

The peak current for peak 11a increased with increasing concentration of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole upto about 1.0 mM. At concentrations

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammograms of 0.5 mM 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole at PGE in phosphate buffers of different pH.

greater than 1.0 mM, the peak current values were more or less constant whereas in the concentration range 0.1–1.0 mM the peak current versus concentration plot can be approximated as a straight line. This behaviour suggests the role of adsorption in the electrode process⁹.

TABLE 1—COULOMETRIC n -VALUES OBSERVED FOR ELECTRO-OXIDATION OF 5-AMINO-3-METHYLISOTHIAZOLE IN PHOSPHATE BUFFERS OF DIFFERENT pH

pH	Concn mM	Potential V vs SCE	Observed n -values*
3.0	0.2	1.2	2.14
	0.5	1.2	2.10
5.4	0.1	1.0	1.96
	0.2	1.0	1.88
	0.5	1.0	2.18
6.8	0.2	1.0	1.86
	0.5	1.0	2.05
8.8	0.2	0.8	2.11
	0.5	0.8	2.04
10.9	0.2	0.8	1.96
	0.5	0.8	1.99

*Average of at least two replicate measurements.

Controlled-potential electrolysis of 0.5 mM solution of compound 1 generally took more than 4 h for complete electro-oxidation. The longer electrolysis time required by 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole is probably due to its adsorption at the surface of the electrode. The values of n determined at different concentrations in the entire pH range indicated the involvement of 2 ± 0.15 electrons and are presented in Table 1.

Spectral studies : The uv spectra of compound 1 was recorded at different pH to determine the pK_a of the compound. 5-Amino-3-methylisothiazole exhibited two well-defined maxima at 235 and 280 nm below pH 5.0. At pH > 5.0, the maximum at longer wavelength shifted to 262 nm. The λ_{max} values were plotted against pH and the dissociation curve obtained exhibited an inflection at pH 5.6. Thus it was concluded that below $pK_a \sim 5.6$, compound 1 largely exists as a protonated species whereas at pH > 5.6 it exists as a neutral species. This pK_a value was further confirmed by S-shaped pH-titration curve and the break in E_p vs pH plot at pH 5.6 also supported the pK_a value of compound 1. It has been reported in the literature¹⁰ that when a N-containing heterocyclic ring possesses amino group, the protonation at amino group is preceded, hence the species exist in the solution are

The progress of electro-oxidation was monitored by recording uv spectra of compound 1 at pH 3.0 and 7.0 in the range 220–350 nm to get information about the uv absorbing intermediate generated during the reaction. The uv spectrum of compound 1 at pH 7.0 exhibited two well-defined λ_{max} at 235 and 262 nm (Curve 1, Fig. 3). Upon application of potential more positive to peak 11a, the absorbance at both the λ_{max} decreased systematically and an increase in absorbance at longer wavelength (290–350 nm) was observed. Curve 7 was recorded after 5 h of electrolysis and exhibited a maximum at 305 nm. It is thus clear that the product of electro-oxidation absorbs at a longer wavelength in comparison to the starting material. At pH 3.0, the uv spectrum of compound 1 exhibited λ_{max} at 235 and 280 nm. Upon application of potential the absorbance at 235 nm decreased whereas the absorbance at 280 nm decreased with a shift of λ_{max} to 260 nm. However, an increase in absorbance at longer wavelength was also recorded. Thus it is clear that the uv spectral behaviour at pH < pK_a and pH > pK_a is essentially the same.

The progress of electrolysis was also monitored by recording cyclic voltammograms at different

interval of times. A typical cyclic voltammogram observed before electro-oxidation at pH 6.8 is presented in Fig. 4A, and peaks 11a, 1c and 1a are

Fig. 3 Observed spectral changes during electro-oxidation of 0.15 mM 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole at pH 7.0 recorded at an interval of (1) 0, (2) 15, (3) 30, (4) 60, (5) 90 and (6) 180 min of electrolysis; potential applied 1.0 V vs SCE; curve 7 was recorded after 5 h of electrolysis.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole observed at different times of electrolysis in phosphate buffer of pH 7.0.

clearly visible. Curves B and C are recorded after an interval of 30 min and it is observed that peak 11a systematically decreased whereas peaks 1c and 1a increased. Cyclic voltammogram E was recorded after 5 h of electrolysis and did not exhibit peak 11a whereas the peak current for peaks 1c and 1a increased and the colour of the solution changed from colourless to light pink. This cyclic voltammogram of exhaustively electrolysed solution of compound 1 did not change even when the electrolysed solution was allowed to stand for several more hours at room temperature. Thus it is concluded that the product of electro-oxidation of compound 1 is electroactive in nature.

Product identification : For the identification of products the electrolysed solution at pH 3.0 and 7.0 was lyophilised (see Experimental) and the ether extract was analysed by tlc which exhibited a single spot with R_f value of 0.42. This clearly indicates that only one product is formed by the complete electro-oxidation of compound 1 in phosphate buffers of different pH. The ir spectrum of compound 1 exhibited bands at 340 and 1320 cm^{-1} corresponding to primary amino group. The ir spectrum of the product did not exhibit these peaks indicating thereby that electro-oxidation of

the product of compound 1 exhibited a sharp band at 1640 cm^{-1} corresponding to an azo or quinone group in the molecule. However, the mass spectral studies supported the presence of $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group in the molecule and a clear molecular ion peak at $m/z=224$ indicated the formation of proposed azo compound. The other high mass peaks with a significant relative abundance observed in the fragmentation pattern were at 126 (16.2%), 125 (11.1%), 124 (2.6%), 112 (23.5%), 111 (8.2%), 110 (4.1%), 98 (6.2%) and 97 (1.2%); however, no attempt was made to explain the fragmentation pattern.

Redox mechanism : The evidences presented above clearly indicate that electro-oxidation of compound 1 occurs in $2e, 2\text{H}^+$ process to give only one electroactive product which absorbs at longer wavelength in comparison to the starting material. The following mechanism can be proposed for the electro-oxidation of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole. As oxidation is taking place at amino group of compound 1, in the first step a loss of $1e, 1\text{H}^+$ will give a free radical species (2), which can readily dimerise to give the hydrazo compound (3). The formation of free radical by $1e, 1\text{H}^+$ oxidation of aromatic amino compounds has been reported by large number of workers^{12,13}. As the free radical (2) will be highly unstable, it can also gain an electron and a proton to give compound 1, which was clearly observed in peak 11c reaction at higher sweep rates. The peak 11c is very small since 2 passes on to 3 (fast) and as such will be of very low concentration. Compound 3 possesses $-\text{NH}-\text{NH}-$ linkage, which is oxidisable at less positive potential than the compound 1, hence it further undergoes $2e, 2\text{H}^+$ oxidation to give the azo compound (4), whose structure finds support from ir and mass spectral data. As compound 4 has more extensive π -conjugation, it will absorb at longer wavelength in comparison to the starting material and thus explains the observed spectral behaviour. Also compound 4 possesses an electroactive $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group; it undergoes $2e, 2\text{H}^+$ reduction to give hydrazo product in peak 1c reaction and the conversion of hydrazo compound to azo compound is observed in peak 1a process. A large number of azo compounds have been found to exhibit such behaviour in aqueous and non-aqueous media^{14,15}. The formation of azo compound as the final product of electro-oxidation has also been reported by other workers for the electrochemical oxidation of substituted thiazole^{16,17} and aminobenzothiazole¹⁸.

Scheme 1. Tentative mechanism proposed for the electro-oxidation of 5-amino-3-methylisothiazole.

5-amino-3-methylisothiazole takes place at primary amino group. Isothiazole ring has also been reported stable to oxidation with a variety of oxidising agents¹¹. Further, the ir spectrum of

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